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The Effects of Organizational Communication, Quality of Work Life, and Work Environment on Improving Employee Performance

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Abstract

Human resources have a very important role in efforts to achieve the goals of an organization or company, both in small and large organizations or companies. The purpose of this study is to determine the effect of effective organizational communication, quality of work life, and work environment on improving employee performance at PT. Astra Honda Motor Sampurna. The population in this study were all employees working in this company with the number of samples taken as many as the population of 32 people. Thus, the sampling technique used in this study was in the form of saturated sampling (census). Meanwhile, the research method used in this study is included in quantitative research, with data processing and analysis techniques in the form of multiple regression analysis. A brief conclusion from the results of this study shows that partially the quality of work life and work environment do not show a significant effect on employee performance, while organizational communication has a significant effect on employee performance. Meanwhile, organizational communication, quality of work life, and work environment simultaneously have a significant effect on employee performance.

Keywords: Organizational Communication, Quality of Work Life, Work Environment, Employee Performance

1. Introduction

It is important to know that human resources have a very important role in improving the quality of work that is increasingly more competitive, high quality, and able to adapt to all the challenges of environmental change faced by an organization or company. The important role of human resources has proven that their roles and functions cannot be replaced by other resources. Even though an organization or company has very large capital to increase the rotation of its business wheels, without human resources capable of driving it, in addition to being able to work optimally, the business run by the organization or company will not run well. Therefore, it is necessary to have good and professional management of the human resources owned by an organization or company, so that when working, each person is able to show the best possible work performance aimed at achieving organizational goals effectively and efficiently.

PT. Astra Honda Motor Sampurna is a company engaged in the sales of spare parts and services for Honda brand motorbikes with a total of 32 employees working. This company was founded on. April 25 2003 located on Jl. Surapati No. 185, Sukaluyu, Bandung City. The vision of this company is to make the company a market leader and motorbike service provider in Indonesia and world-class, by realizing consumers' dreams and contributing to Indonesian society. In order to achieve this vision, companies need employees who are able to work optimally because employees have a very important role in maintaining the sustainability of the business run by a company.

Table 1: Target and Realization of PT Employee Performance. Astra Honda Motor Sampurna Period 2018 to. 2022

No	Performance Indicators	Target (%)	Realization (%)				
			2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
1	Employee Attendance	100	92	91	85	88	96
2	Making Purchase and Inventory Reports	100	100	100	67	58	100
3	Development of Mechanical Quality (Coaching)	100	100	75	0	0	100
4	Acceptance of Services	100	94	85	72	77	85
5	Spare Parts Sales (Spare Part)	100	93	87	71	82	91

Source: Company Performance Report, 2023

The data shown in table 1 shows that the actual performance achievements of employees working for this company still show work results that are not very satisfactory, even though in 2018 and 2020 there are still several work indicators that have been able to achieve the predetermined work target percentage. However, over all the work results shown by employees working at this company are still considered not very good, there is even one work indicator that in 2020 and 2021, namely coaching for mechanical quality, did not reach the work target percentage at all which has been previously determined.

Defined by Sedarmayanti (2013) that employee performance as the result of work in terms of quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him. Several dimensions and indicators are used as measures in assessing employee work results at work, including (Robbins & Judge, 2015): 1) Work quality, namely measuring work results based on employee perceptions of the quality of work produced, as well as perfection in carrying out tasks which is carried out using the employee's skills and abilities, with several indicators in the form of the employee's level of neatness and thoroughness in carrying out the task; 2) Quantity, namely the amount produced which is often expressed in terms such as the number of units or the number of activity cycles completed, with several indicators in the form of the employee's level of achievement in completing the work and the level of work volume with the employee's abilities; 3) Punctuality, namely the level of activity that can be completed at the beginning of the stated time, as well as maximizing the time available to carry out other activities, with several indicators in the form of the level of employees completing their work on time and efficiently, as well as the level of employees carrying out their tasks quickly; 4) Effectiveness, namely the level of use of organizational resources (energy, money, technology and raw materials) which can be maximized with the aim of increasing the results of each unit in the use of resources, with the indicator being the level of employees using the right facilities and infrastructure in carrying out work ; and 5) Independence, namely the level of an employee who is able to carry out his work function without asking for guidance from a supervisor or asking for supervisors to intervene in the work, with several indicators in the form of the employee's level of courage to bear the risks of work, and the level of employee completing work without the help of colleagues.

It should be noted that one of the factors that is thought to be the cause of an increase or decrease in work performance or employee work results at work, among them is the organizational communication factor. Often, if communication between superiors and subordinates does not go well, for example employees who do not understand their assignments correctly, or misinterpret orders given by their superiors or superiors, can result in the orders given not being carried out properly, thus having an impact on employee work performance decreases. Increasingly disharmonious working relationships between fellow employees during work, as a result of very poor communication patterns which give rise to frequent conflicts between superiors and subordinates or between employees, can have an impact on employee performance that is increasingly poor, even impacting also bad for the company's overall performance.

Several previous research results show that organizational communication can have a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This is proven through a study from Ernika, D. (2016) which states that good communication can be the right means for improving employee performance. This means that if the exchange of information can be carried out very well, completely and smoothly, it is hoped that employees can carry out their duties and responsibilities correctly and this will have a good impact on employee performance. Likewise with the opinion of Triana, A, et al. (2016) who concluded that organizational communication has a significant effect on employee performance. This means that if organizational communication runs very well and effectively, employee performance will increase. However, effective communication does not always have an impact on better employee performance. This is proven by a study by Syukur, A., Supriyono, E., & Suparwati, Y. K. (2019) which concluded that by not talking more with co-workers or other people, employees will become more focused at work, resulting in productivity work is increasing.

Mulyana, D (2011) defines organizational communication as the display and interpretation of messages between communication units that are part of a particular organization, in other words consisting of communication units in a hierarchical relationship with each other and functioning in an environment. Several indicators of organizational communication effectiveness include (A.W. Suranto, 2011): 1) Comprehension, namely the ability to understand the message carefully as intended by the communicator; 2) Pleasure, where the purpose of communication is not just to transact messages, but is also intended to interact with each other in a pleasant way to foster human relationships; 3) Influence on attitude, namely the ability of a communicant to change his attitude according to the message he receives; 4) Improved relations, where an effective communication process can inadvertently increase the level of international relations; and 5) Action, where both parties communicating take action in accordance with the message being communicated.

Quality of work life has a very important function in efforts to improve employee performance. If someone has, or is able to achieve a high quality of work life, then the performance shown by that person can become increasingly better and also have an impact on achieving the organizational goals that have been set. As stated by Wibowo (2007), improving the quality of workers' lives has a crucial role in efforts to increase work productivity. If an organization is able to improve working environment conditions that make employees feel comfortable at work, then employees will automatically work with higher levels of productivity because employees are able to devote all their thoughts to showing their best work performance while working, and working to achieve goals. organization. However, sometimes a working atmosphere that feels safe and comfortable can have an impact on better employee performance. This is demonstrated by the opinion of Asharini, Hardyastuti, and Irham (2018) who state that quality of work life (QWL) does not have a significant effect on improving employee performance.

Defined by Bernardin & Russell (1993), that the quality of work life is the level of an individual (employee) in meeting his or her personal needs (a need for freedom) as long as the individual is still employed. The opinion expressed by Luthans (2006) states that the quality of work life is the impact of human and organizational effectiveness combined with an emphasis on problem solving and decision making. In this way, it is said that the quality of work life is an employee's perception of the well-being and work atmosphere in the workplace, and refers to how effectively the work environment can meet the employee's needs. Several indicators that can be used as a measure in assessing the quality of a person's work life include (Bernadin & Russell, 1993): 1) Growth and Development, namely the opportunity for employees to develop all their skills and performance in the challenges of carrying out a job within the organization; 2) Participation, namely the opportunity given to employees by the

organization to make decisions and be responsible for their work; 3) Physical Environment, namely the employee's feeling of comfort in the workplace environment which is able to increase work productivity; 4) Supervision, namely a good relationship between the leader and his employees, as well as the ability of a leader to work in a team and provide clear direction regarding the work that must be done by his employees, so that the work can be completed well; 5) Pay and Benefits, namely the opportunity for employees to receive wages/salaries in accordance with their workload; 6) Social Relevance, namely good relationships with colleagues in completing work and other aspects of life at work; and 7) Workplace Integration, namely good relationships with colleagues in forming a work team to complete a job.

Another factor that is thought to have an influence on improving employee performance is the work environment factor. If an organization is able to create a positive work environment, employees tend to be able to show better performance results while working. On the other hand, if an organization is unable to create and maintain a good work environment, it will be difficult for employees to show their best performance at work. Often, by creating a work environment that is able to provide recognition for work achievements, as well as challenges in work and employee career development, employee work motivation will increase, which will also have an impact on improving employee performance. Likewise, if the work environment created is able to provide a feeling of security and comfort, and pays attention to work-life balance for employees, then the level of employee welfare will be higher, which will lead to increased work productivity. As stated by Badrianto, Y., & Ekhsan, M. (2020) who stated that the work environment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Likewise, the opinion of Rorong, S. V. (2016) concluded that the physical work environment has a significant effect on improving employee performance. In his study, it was stated that room temperature and humidity can be an important element that contributes to improving employee performance. In addition, several other elements of the physical work environment play an important role in efforts to increase employee work productivity, including good work space lighting, the absence of loud noises, a clean, safe and comfortable work space. However, the work environment does not always have a positive effect on improving employee performance. This is demonstrated through a study from Bahri, S. (2019) which states that the work environment has an insignificant effect on employee performance.

Affandi (2018) defines the work environment as everything that is around employees and can influence them in carrying out the tasks assigned to them, for example by having air conditioner (AC), adequate lighting, and so on. Several indicators that can be used as benchmarks in assessing the condition of the work environment in an organization include (Nitisemito, 2014): 1) The physical work environment which includes factors such as: a) Lighting in the workplace, where workplace lighting is good. sufficient to assist the organization's success in carrying out its operational activities; b) Air circulation, where sufficient air exchange is required in each work space to help increase the physical freshness of employees while working; c) Layout, where each employee should have a comfortable work space to complete their work well; d) Facilities, where the availability of complete facilities can be a supporting factor for employees in carrying out their daily work activities; e) Security, where the sense of security felt by the employee can help the employee to remain enthusiastic at work and demonstrate the best work performance; and 2) Non-physical work environment which includes several factors as follows: a) Relationships with co-workers, where each employee is able to work well together among groups which results in their work being completed more quickly and easily; b) Work atmosphere, namely the conditions around employees who are doing work which can influence the implementation of the work itself; c) Attention and support from superiors, namely the extent to which employees feel that superiors often provide direction, confidence, attention and respect for them; d) Work responsibility, namely the extent to which employees feel that their work can understand and be responsible for their actions; e) Relationship between superiors and subordinates, where good and harmonious relationships are created between leaders and their members, employee performance will increase.

Based on this explanation, the author became interested in conducting research with the following title: "The Effects of Organizational Communication, Quality of Work Life, and Work Environment on Improving Employee Performance."

2. Method

Judging from the relationship between variables, this research is included in causal associative research which aims to find out and analyze the relationship between one variable and another variable, so that it can be seen how one variable can influence or be influenced by other variables (Umar, 2015). Meanwhile, if you look at the data used, this research is included in quantitative research, namely research based on data in the form of numbers and numbers (Suliyanto, 2005). The aim of this research is to find out whether organizational communication, quality of work life, and a conducive work environment can have a significant effect on improving employee performance at PT. Astra Honda Motor Sampurna.

The main variables in this research are the variables Organizational Communication (X1), Quality of Work Life (X2), and Work Environment (X3) which act as the independent variables, as well as the Employee Performance variable (Y), which acts as the dependent variable. It is stated that population is a generalized area consisting of objects or subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then conclusions drawn (Sugiyono, 2019). Meanwhile, it is stated that the sample is part of the population that has certain characteristics or conditions that will be studied (Riduwan, 2007). In this research, the population and sample are all employees who work at PT. Astra Honda Motor Sampurna, totaling 32 people. In connection with the number of samples taken having the same size as the population, the sampling technique used in this research is the census method or saturated sampling which, if defined, is the sampling technique used if all members of the population are used as samples.

Judging from the source, the data required in this research is divided into two sources, including: 1) Primary data sources, namely data sources that directly provide data to data collectors, or data obtained directly from the original source, where In this research, primary data was obtained through interviews and distributing questionnaires distributed to employees who work at PT. Astra Honda Motor Sampurna as the respondent; 2) Secondary data sources, namely data sources that indirectly provide data to data collectors, or data obtained indirectly from the original source, and are used as supporting data for research results obtained through library or literature studies. It should also be noted that the data collection techniques used in this research were carried out in various ways, including: 1) Literature study, namely a theoretical study used to collect relevant data that is in accordance with the research topic, whether the data is sourced. from books, news, national and international journal articles, as well as other trusted sources; 2) Questionnaire, which is a method of collecting data which is carried out by distributing a set of questions or written statements which are distributed to respondents for them to answer; 3) Interview, which is a method of collecting data which is carried out when the researcher wishes to carry out a preliminary study to find the problem under study, and also aims to find out everything from the respondent in more depth with a small number of respondents. In this research, interviews were conducted by asking directly an employee who holds the position of service advisor in this company with the aim of obtaining as much data or information as possible related to this research problem; 4) Observation, namely a method of collecting data whose process is aimed at understanding, knowing and exploring an object which involves direct monitoring of the object being studied.

Meanwhile, for the data processing and analysis techniques used in this research, multiple regression analysis was carried out, with hypothesis testing (t and F tests) calculated using the SPSS version 23.0 program.

3. Results

The following is a table showing the results of simultaneous hypothesis testing:

Table 2: Hypothesis Testing (F Test)

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3629.342	3	1209.781	11.598	.000 ^b
	Residual	2920.658	28	104.309		
	Total	6550.000	31			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Work Environment, Quality of Work Life, Organizational Communication
Source: Processed data, 2024

Based on the data shown in table 2, it is known that if the r value is not greater than the α level used, namely 0.05, or $0.000 < 0.05$, then H_0 is rejected, which means that organizational communication and the quality of work life have a significant effect on employee performance.

Table 3: Multiple Regression of the Effect of Organizational Communication, Quality of Work Life and Work Environment on Increasing Employee Performance

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	37.578	24.437		1.538	.135
	Communication	1.193	.230	.662	5.193	.000
	Quality	.186	.099	.244	1.881	.070
	Environment	-.265	.219	-.157	-1.212	.235

a. Dependent Variable: Kinerja

Source: Processed data, 2024

The data shows that:

- A constant of 37,578 means that if changes occur in Organizational Communication, Quality of Work Life and Work Environment, the value of Employee Performance is 37,578.
- Organizational Communication (Variable X1) has a positive value of 1,193, which means that higher Organizational Communication (X1) can increase the value of Employee Performance by 1.193.
- Quality of Work Life (Variable X2) has a positive value of 0.186, which means that a higher Quality of Work Life (X2) can increase the value of Employee Performance by 0.186.
- Work Environment (Variable X3) has a negative value of 0.265, which means that a higher Work Environment (X3) can reduce the value of Employee Performance by 0.265.

Based on the data shown in table 3, it is known that the t_{count} value (5.193) has a value with a number greater than the t_{table} value (2.042), which means that H_0 is rejected, so that the Organizational Communication variable (X1) has a significant influence on the Employee Performance variable (Y).

Based on the data shown in table 3, it is known that the t_{count} value (1.881) has a smaller value compared to the t_{table} value (2.042), which means that H_0 is accepted, so that the Quality of Work Life variable (X2) shows an insignificant influence on the Performance variable. Employee (Y).

Based on the data shown in table 3, it is known that the t_{count} value (-1.212) has a value with a smaller number than the t_{table} value (2.042), which means that H_0 is accepted, so that the Work Environment variable (X3) shows an insignificant influence on the variable Employee Performance (Y).

Table 4: Coefficient of Determination (R^2) of the Effect of Organizational Communication, Quality of Work Life, and Work Environment on Employee Performance

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.744 ^a	.554	.506	10.213

a. Predictors: (Constant), X3, X2, X1

b. Dependent Variable: Y

Source: Processed data, 2024

The measurement of the coefficient of determination (R^2) is defined as a measurement that aims to determine the extent to which a research model can explain variations in the independent variables with values ranging between 0 and 1.

The visible data shows that the coefficient of determination (adjusted R^2) of the variables studied is 0.554, which means that a 55% increase in employee performance can be determined by how effective the communication between superiors and subordinates is, the ability of workers to meet their needs through work. what they do, as well as how conducive the work environment is felt by employees. Therefore, the influence shown by the three independent variables, namely the variables Organizational Communication (X1), Quality of Work Life (X2), and Work Environment (X3), on the dependent variable in the form of Employee Performance (Y) is 55%, while the remaining 45% is determined by other factors that are not used as variables that are thought to influence the dependent variable.

4. Discussion

4.1. The Influence of Organizational Communication on Employee Performance

The research results show that the effectiveness of communication in an organization can be one of the factors that influences the increasing work performance of employees at work. This means that as communication becomes more effective between fellow employees while working, the better the work results demonstrated by these employees in carrying out their duties and functions in accordance with their respective positions. Therefore, without effective communication, it is difficult for employees to show their best performance at work, which also results in the overall organizational goals not being achieved. As expressed by Kuswarno, E. (2001), the main problems of the organizational communication process that determine organizational effectiveness include: 1) message (information) processing process, where problems often arise if there are differences in meaning between the sender of the message and message recipients, as well as excessive information that can give rise to negative reactions from communication participants; and 2) organizational communication style. Meanwhile, the opinion expressed by Nurrohm, H., & Anatan, L. (2009) states that several things need to be considered by a communicator in creating effective communication, including the ability to identify targets who are recipients of messages, determining communication goals. designing messages, selecting media and message sources, and collecting feedback. Similar to the research results expressed by Islami, A. N., Palupi, M. F. T., & Romadhan, M. I. (2021) which concluded that if organizational communication increases, employee performance will also increase. A similar opinion was also expressed by Riono, S. B., Syaifulloh, M., & Utami, S. N. (2020) through his study which states that high or good organizational communication will be followed by increased employee performance.

4.2. The Influence of Quality of Work Life on Employee Performance

The research results show that the quality of work life does not always play an important role in efforts to improve employee performance. This shows that improvements in the quality of work life are not always accompanied by better work results shown by employees during work. As stated by Asrini, Hardyastuti, and Irham (2018) in their study, quality of work life (QWL) does not have a significant effect on increasing employee performance, either directly or indirectly through other variables, such as organizational commitment. In this way, it seems that there are still other exogenous factors or variables that have a greater influence on improving employee performance. However, several other studies actually show that there is a significant influence of the quality of work life on increasing employee performance, either directly or indirectly through other intermediary variables. One of them is shown by the results of a study from Sari, Bendesa & Antara (2019) which states that quality of work life (QWL) directly has a positive and significant influence on employee performance, or indirectly through the intermediary variables job satisfaction and work motivation. Another opinion was expressed by Setyaningrum and Ekhsan (2021) who stated that there needs to be a variable that can mediate the relationship between quality of work life (QWL) and employee performance, namely job satisfaction.

4.3. The Influence of the Work Environment on Employee Performance

The research results show that creating a conducive work environment in an organization is not always the most crucial factor that can influence improving employee performance. This means that as the working environment is getting better for employees while working, it does not necessarily mean that employee performance results will

be better than before. The results of this research seem to have a different perspective from several previous research results which actually show that there is a significant influence of the work environment on improving employee performance. As the results of the study shown by Joseph (2016) concluded that the physical and non-physical work environment has a significant influence on increasing employee work productivity, both partially and simultaneously. A similar conclusion was also shown by Setiyanto & Natalia (2017) who stated that the physical and non-physical work environment had a positive and significant effect on the level of employee work productivity. However, several other studies have similar results to this research, including the opinion expressed by Hanafi, B. D., & Yohana, C. (2017) which states that the work environment does not have a significant influence on employee performance.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results of the research and discussion, it is concluded that: 1) Organizational communication has a significant effect on employee performance, which means that as the communication between fellow members in an organization becomes more effective, the better the performance shown by its members will be. while working; 2) The quality of work life does not have a significant effect on improving employee performance, which means that creating an increasingly harmonious work atmosphere does not always have an impact on increasing employee performance; 3) The work environment does not have a significant effect on improving employee performance, which means that as the work environment becomes more conducive, it does not mean that the employee's performance is getting better. 4) Organizational communication, quality of work life and work environment have a significant effect on employee performance.

It should be realized that this research still has several limitations in its implementation and presentation. Therefore, so that in the future this research can be carried out even better, it is necessary to add several other variables which are thought to have an influence on the work results shown by employees during work, such as leadership, work motivation, workload, work stress, program effectiveness. training and development, job placement, etc., in addition to needing to involve several other similar companies as units of analysis, so that the number of respondents involved becomes increasingly large.

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